

Research Paper

Distributed geothermal response test on a 750 m deep borehole thermal energy storage system

Lukas Seib^{a,*}, Matthias Krusemark^a, Clemens Lehr^b, Max Ohagen^a, Hung Pham^a, Markus Schedel^a, Bastian Welsch^c, Ingo Sass^{a,d}

^a Technical University of Darmstadt, Institute of Applied Geosciences, Geothermal Science and Technology, Schnittspahnstraße 9, 64287 Darmstadt, Germany

^b Geotechnisches Umweltbüro Lehr, 61231 Bad Nauheim, Germany

^c Bochum University of Applied Sciences, Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering & Energy Transition Institute EnWI, Am Hochschulcampus 1, 44801 Bochum, Germany

^d GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Section 4.3: Geoenergy, Telegrafenberg, 14473 Potsdam, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Medium-deep borehole thermal energy storage (MD-BTES) systems are a promising solution for large-scale thermal energy storage, but their optimization requires a detailed understanding of subsurface thermal properties. In this study, a distributed geothermal response test (dGRT) was conducted on one of three 750 m coaxial boreholes of an MD-BTES demonstrator system using fiber optic temperature measurements. Local thermal conductivity was found to vary significantly, ranging from 2.0 to 2.8 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹, reflecting the transition from fractured basalt to granodiorite within the storage reservoir. The borehole thermal resistance decreased steadily with depth, from 0.04 to 0.01 m K W⁻¹, reflecting better thermal coupling at greater depths and demonstrating the effectiveness of a low thermal conductivity grout in the upper borehole section. Numerical simulations based on the GRT results yielded high accuracy, particularly when based on depth-resolved temperature profiles. However, the analysis also revealed challenges, including significant heat loss from the inner pipe to the annulus at elevated temperatures, which likely reduces MD-BTES system efficiency. These findings highlight the capability of dGRT to provide high-quality thermal property data for medium-depth systems and offer insights into design optimizations for future MD-BTES installations.

1. Introduction

The efficient design of the heat supply using new technologies is of great importance to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Many renewable heat sources, such as solar thermal collectors, face the challenge of seasonal variability, where heat generated during summer often exceeds demand, leading to a waste of energy. In winter, however, the demand for heat is significantly higher than what solar thermal energy can sustainably supply without building an uneconomically large capacity. The solution to this challenge is seasonal storage, where the surplus summer heat is stored for winter use. One established technology for seasonal heat storage is borehole thermal energy storage (BTES), where heat is stored in the natural subsurface using borehole heat exchangers (BHE). BTES consists of multiple BHE, conventionally no deeper than 200 m [1,2]. A recently realized advancement is medium-deep BTES (MD-BTES), which allows for the effective storage of excess heat in deeper

subsurface regions, offering greater insulation from groundwater and reducing temperature increase in aquifers [3]. Numerical studies suggest that MD-BTES systems can store multiple GWh of thermal energy annually with recovery rates of up to 83 % [4]. MD-BTES differ from deep borehole heat exchangers (DBHE) [5] because of their intended purpose and array layout. MD-BTES are designed for optimal heat storage performance. Thus, the spacing of the BHE is chosen to be small enough to allow for interaction between the BHE while simultaneously maximizing storage volume.

To test the MD-BTES concept, a demonstrator site consisting of three 750-meter BHEs was constructed in Darmstadt, Germany, from 2022 to 2023 [6,7]. A distributed Geothermal Response Test (dGRT) was performed on one of the BHEs to determine the thermal properties specific to the Darmstadt site before the test operation of the system.

The GRT, also often referred to as TRT (Thermal Response Test), is a common method for in situ determination of the effective in-situ thermal

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: seib@geo.tu-darmstadt.de (L. Seib).

properties of a borehole heat exchanger system [8]. A GRT provides a global value of the borehole thermal resistance, which combines all thermal resistances between the working fluid and the borehole wall [9] and the effective thermal conductivity of the surrounding subsurface, which are the two governing parameters for heat transfer in and around a borehole heat exchanger [10]. The method was first described theoretically by Mogensen [11] with a constant heat extraction, based on volume flow, inlet, and outlet temperature measurements. Today, however, mostly constant heating is applied in GRT for simplicity. A GRT measurement can be supplemented by fiber optic temperature measurements based on the distributed temperature sensing (DTS) method [12–15]. In a distributed geothermal response test (dGRT), the thermal conductivity and the thermal borehole resistivity can be determined with a certain spatial resolution along the borehole [16]. This allows more detailed geological investigations of heterogeneities or local groundwater flow zones.

The test site layout includes three BHE (numbered BHE 2 to BHE 4, Fig. 1) and three groundwater monitoring wells (GWM 1 to 3). The central BHE 1 is only drilled up to 40 m and was not completed. In addition to assessing the thermophysical rock properties necessary for modeling, the dGRT aimed to evaluate the internal thermal short-circuiting – i.e., the heat loss from the inner to the outer pipe – due to the substantial length of 750 m and the unique, cost-effective, patented installation method, which has yet to be fully documented for thermal performance.

The 750 m depth of this project fills a research gap concerning dGRT, as practical studies in this range are limited. For example, Hakala et al. [17] investigated a 300 m deep borehole to determine groundwater flow and thermal properties of the crystalline bedrock, while McDaniel et al. [18] performed a dGRT on a 97.5 m borehole in sedimentary units. Lehr and Sass [19] explored a 400 m deep borehole in a karst aquifer to determine the thermal and hydraulic parameters with enhanced geothermal response tests (eGRT). Holmberg [20] analyzed the characteristics of deeper coaxial BHE up to 1000 m numerically. They validated the models on a dGRT of a 190 m well analyzed previously by

Acuña et al. [21]. Morchio et al. [22] investigated the performance of a GRT with a validated model. They found that in classical GRT evaluations, measurements with an inlet through the annulus have accuracy advantages over an inlet through the inner pipe. Radioti et al. [23] investigated the thermal properties of a 100 m double-U type BHE in Belgium with a rather long 7-month GRT with the results that a typical 60 h GRT can be representative also of the long-term behavior of BHE. Furthermore, it was concluded, that the temperature evolution in the bedrock surrounding the BHE is highly dependable on the applied heat load and less on the rock heterogeneity.

Only Ma et al. [24] have done investigations along a medium-deep BHE by testing the use of one 2000 m borehole out of an array in Tianjin, China [25] for its heat storage and production potential. However, they did not investigate the borehole characteristics in detail. This lack of experimental data for medium-deep systems underlines the importance of studies like this, as MD-BTES and medium-deep BHE can apply to a wide range of environments and uses [26].

In medium-deep BHE, coaxial systems are commonly used because of their mechanical stability [27] and thermal performance. They consist of an outer tube and an inner tube, allowing for a downflow and upflow path for the working fluid (Fig. 2). Standard API steel pipes are used in this project. Moreover, the inner pipe is fitted with a polypropylene liner to minimize thermal short-circuiting, which is segmented to manage thermal expansion and mechanical stress due to buoyancy forces. There are also alternatives to insulating the inner pipe [28,29]. For example, the use of inner pipes made entirely of polymer, which however quickly reach their mechanical load limits with increasing depth. Other options for insulating the inner pipe, such as vacuum pipes, are available but come at a higher cost [28].

The effect of thermal short circuits between the downflowing and upflowing fluid of coaxial BHE has already been investigated [31], with primary influencing factors identified as the temperature difference between the downflow and upflow, the properties of the inner pipe, and the flow rate, which determines the residence time of the working fluid [26,32]. This issue is particularly relevant to MD-BTES due to the

Fig. 1. Layout of the MD-BTES test site with three BHE (2–4) and three groundwater monitoring wells (GWM 1–3) (Modified after [30]).

Fig. 2. BHE layout and simplified geological units encountered during drilling based on cutting samples and borehole geophysics (Modified after [30]).

extended length, as the increased distance for heat transfer can impact efficiency [20,31].

Experimental data on medium-deep to deep borehole heat exchanger systems is very scarce. However, experimental data is imperative to gain detailed understanding of the behaviour of such BHE and is essential for the assessment of the predictive capability of numerical models. This study presents the results of a dGRT conducted on the MD-BTES system in Darmstadt, providing a unique dataset that offers valuable experimental insights into the thermal efficiency and behavior of BHE at medium depths. Consequently, the present study fills a research gap in the experimental investigation of medium-deep to deep borehole heat exchangers. Moreover, the thermal behavior of the insulation method used for the inner pipe of this system has not yet been investigated and

represents a promising low-cost alternative for future projects. As the study was conducted with temperatures of almost 70 °C, the dataset is novel. It covers the system’s properties close to its maximum operating temperature of 90 °C. By examining the effects of thermal short-circuiting, rock thermal properties, and heat transfer dynamics along the 750 m borehole, this research furthermore contributes to a deeper understanding of the performance and feasibility of MD-BTES systems for seasonal heat storage. These findings are particularly relevant given the limited experimental data on medium-deep systems.

2. Methodology

GRT measurements were conducted on one BHE (BHE 2) out of three

Fig. 3. Initial temperature and temperature during the GRT at one timestep.

existing BHE on the Lichtwiese campus in Darmstadt, Germany (Fig. 1). The campus is situated in the northern foothills of the Odenwald crystalline complex. Locally, the drill site is positioned right next to a lithological boundary between two Variscan granodiorite complexes and Permian basaltic and sedimentary (Rotliegend) units whose contact is likely characterized by fault activity. The borehole first passes through 180 m of interbedded Permian basalts and sedimentary rocks and then extends into the Variscan granites and granodiorites of the Odenwald crystalline complex. The alteration grade of the granitoids decreases with depth [33]. At the base of the borehole, the undisturbed temperature is 27.1 °C, resulting in a geothermal gradient of 22 °C km⁻¹ (Fig. 3). Further discussion of the geologic framework of the site can be found in [34].

The borehole completion comprises a 12" steel casing up to a depth of 40 m, followed by a 7" steel casing down to 750 m (Fig. 2). Inside this casing, a 4.5" inner steel pipe with a 3.9" PPR (polypropylene) liner was installed for thermal insulation. Two clearances of approximately 5 m in length each were integrated between the PPR segments to accommodate thermal expansion for temperatures up to 90 °C (Fig. 2). Two types of grout material were used: low-conductivity cement (0.6 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹) up to 180 m to insulate the shallow groundwater and high-conductivity cement (3.0 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹) for the remaining depth to optimize heat transfer.

2.1. Experimental Set-Up

The dGRT measurement was carried out for 42 days in October and November 2023 using pure tap water as the heat transfer fluid. A 150 kW heating unit provided the required heating load for the experiments. A heating output of 150 kW (equivalent to a specific heat injection rate of 200 W m⁻¹) represents an exceptionally elevated value for a GRT. In comparable studies, the heat injection rate ranges from 10 to 30 W m⁻¹ [9,35]. The rationale behind the selection of a high heat output is to facilitate the simultaneous testing of the BHE's general behavior at elevated temperatures, alongside the GRT, for potential future applications.

The fluid circuit, driven by an external pump, begins in the heating unit (Fig. 4a). To compensate for thermal expansion, the water first flows into an insulated buffer tank before entering the BHE and flowing down the inner pipe. It returns to the surface via the annulus and then from the wellhead back to the heater. After the heating period, the heating unit and the pump were switched off and the cooling process

continued to be monitored via the fiber optic cables.

The controller and data loggers for the installed sensors are located in a construction container near the BHE. These include the fiber optic controller, the pump controller, and the data logger for the temperature and flow sensors (Fig. 4b). Three fiber optic cables are installed in the borehole: A hybrid single-mode cable with two loose tubes and two tight buffered 9 μm fibers was installed together with the casing attached to the centralizers and is located in the grout (Fig. 5).

One multimode cable 50/125 μm is in the annular space, and another is in the inner pipe (Fig. 4). Both multimode cables are positioned in the BHE without additional fixation on either one of the pipes. The single-mode cable is operated with an OTS3 device from LIOS Sensing based on OFDR (optical frequency domain reflectometry) (Fiber Optic Controller 2). The two multimode cables are measured using the OTDR (optical time domain reflectometry) principle with an APSensing N4386A (Fiber Optic Controller 1). In all cases, these are single-end measurements.

Before the measurements, the fiber optic cables were calibrated over multiple depth sections using wireline temperature logs from the borehole and a calibrated temperature bath on the surface [12]. Additionally, a water tank is located within the construction container, wherein 15 m of the DTS cable is positioned alongside two PT1000 sensors for the continuous validation of the recorded DTS values.

To measure the flow rate, two magnetic inductive flow meters were placed in the inlet and outlet of the BHE. Furthermore, two ultrasonic flow meters were also used for redundancy. Moreover, four screw-in PT100 temperature sensors are installed: two in the BHE inlet and two in the outlet (Fig. 4b).

2.2. Evaluation method

The GRT is evaluated with three different methods: Two global approaches where a single value for effective thermal conductivity and a global borehole thermal resistance are acquired. One calculation is based on the arithmetic mean of inlet and outlet fluid temperatures (borehole resistance in this case denoted as R_b) and provides a simplified estimate for system design. The other one is derived from the true mean fluid temperature along the borehole depth based on the DTS measurements (borehole resistance in this case denoted as R_{tb} based on the nomenclature applied in [21]). This is done because the arithmetic mean between in- and outlet temperature assumes constant heat flux along the borehole, which is unrealistic and was found to lead to overestimation of

Fig. 4. GRT measuring setup and hydraulic connection at BHE 2 (drawing not to scale).

Fig. 5. Geometry of the single-mode fiber located in the grout and fixation on the outer BHE pipe with a centralizer.

borehole thermal resistance [36]. The true mean fluid temperature offers a more precise evaluation, accounting for spatial temperature variations [21]. In a third approach, the calibrated glass fiber data is used to evaluate the effective thermal conductivity and local borehole thermal resistance (R_{tb}) in the borehole in 10 m intervals (dGRT).

Only the heating phase is used for the calculation of R_b , as the circulation was stopped after heating. R_{tb} is calculated twice: Once only with heating (R_{tb}) and once with the heating and regeneration phase (R_{tb^*}), which is now available with the glass fiber data. Of course, the addition of the regeneration phase to the calculation should not influence borehole thermal resistance results, which is only relevant when heating is applied. However, there might be slight changes resulting from the fitting procedure. The heating and regeneration phases are also used for the evaluation of the local dGRT.

The evaluation is based on the line source theory [37,38] where T_f is the average temperature [°C], a is the thermal diffusivity [$m^2 s^{-1}$], \dot{Q}_H is the average heat transfer rate [W], H is the effective hole depth [m], λ is the thermal conductivity [$W m^{-1} K^{-1}$], γ is the Euler coefficient [0.5772], R_b is the thermal resistance [$m K W^{-1}$], T_0 is the initial soil temperature [°C], and r is the radius of borehole [m].

$$T_f(t) - T_0 = \frac{\dot{Q}_H}{4\pi \bullet \lambda} \left[\ln \left(\frac{4 \bullet \alpha \bullet t}{r^2} \right) - \gamma \right] + \dot{Q}_H \bullet R_b \quad (1)$$

The superposition principle [39] is applied to take account of the varying heat output over time. This results in the following equation with E_i as the exponential integral and $\Delta v(t)$ being the calculated time-dependent temperature change.

$$\Delta \vartheta(t) = \dot{Q}_{Hi} \left[\frac{R_b}{2\pi} + \frac{1}{4\pi\lambda} E_i \left(\frac{r^2}{4\alpha t} \right) \right] + \sum_{i=2}^n (Q_{Hi} - Q_{Hi-1}) \left[\frac{R_b}{2\pi} + \frac{1}{4\pi\lambda} E_i \left(\frac{r^2}{4\alpha(t - t_{i-1})} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

A detailed description of the evaluation methodology can be found in Raymond et al. [40] or Lehr and Sass [19]. A comprehensive overview of different approaches for GRT evaluation methods is given by Wilke et al. [41]. In the evaluation, the thermal conductivity and the borehole thermal resistance are calculated by minimizing the squared error between the calculated $T_f(t)$ and measured temperature response using the Levenberg-Marquart algorithm for nonlinear least square optimizations in Python [35]. The thermal recovery phase is included in the evaluation

procedure for R_{tb} and R_{tb} as the influence of cable position in the borehole and the influence of R_b , in particular, is reduced at this time [21,42].

For the calculation of the GRT, the averaged heat capacity of 0.85 kJ $kg^{-1} K^{-1}$ with a density of 2700 $kg m^{-3}$ was used for the properties of the subsurface based on a weighted average of regional petrophysical measurements of Granodiorites and Basalts [43]. The fiberoptic cable data in the annulus of the BHE is used for the calculation of the dGRT, as the inner part of the BHE is only in contact with the annulus and local heat transfer to the subsurface is dependent on the annulus temperature. A homogeneous temperature field over the whole flow cross-section is assumed in the inner pipe and annulus.

The evaluation of a dGRT requires depth-resolved heating rates. While an enhanced GRT (eGRT) uses an electrical heating cable to apply an approximately constant heating rate over the entire length of the BHE [19,44], the situation with a dGRT is more complex: the fluid temperature changes over the depth of the borehole due to the heat transfer to the surrounding rock. Changing temperatures in turn mean that the heat input rate itself becomes inhomogeneous [41]. To calculate the depth-resolved heat output, the borehole is divided into 10 m depth intervals. The heat input rate \dot{Q}_H is calculated from the temperature difference between the start and end points of each section [45,46]. This calculation is done for the inner pipe and the annulus and subsequently summed up to find the overall heat loss.

$$\dot{Q}_H(t) = \rho \bullet c_p \bullet V \bullet \Delta T(t) \quad (3)$$

Standard parameters for water at 20 °C and pressure are assumed for the working fluid with a density ρ of 998 $kg m^{-3}$ and heat capacity c_p of 4190 $J kg^{-1} K^{-1}$. Due to the variability of the temperature measurement of the DTS device, the slope of the temperature measurement curve was approximated with a regression based on a third-order polynomial [47].

In addition to the properties of the subsurface, the thermal performance of the BHE itself plays a major role. To investigate this, the fiber optic cables in the inner tube and annulus are used to determine, how much heat from the inflowing fluid is transferred to the outflowing fluid. This was also done by calculation of the specific heat loss in certain depth intervals based on equation (3).

2.3. Numerical model

The GRT measured values are validated numerically using the

software FEFLOW. The aim is to evaluate how well simulations based on the determined effective thermal conductivity and thermal resistance match the data measured in the field. As only a single BHE is operated for the GRT, with no interaction with neighboring BHE, a simplified vertical model is used that neglects the deviation of the BHE from the vertical.

The FEFLOW model has a size of 200 by 200 m. The depth was set to 900 m. A structured mesh of prismatic finite elements was used consisting of 187 mesh layers. The mesh was refined around the BHE position to obtain better calculation results, where high-temperature variations occur (Fig. 6). Vertically the mesh layers have a thickness of 5 m. The vertical refinement is increased to 1.5 m at the grout and geology change is observed in the drilling and the lower end of the BHE. The governing equations of the model are described in detail in [48,49]. The calculated thermal conductivities and the borehole resistances of the GRT as well as the thermal capacity ($0.85 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and density (2700 kg m^{-3}) applied for the GRT are used to parameterize the model. A porosity of 5 % was assumed for the upper basalt section and 3 % for the granite in the lower part of the model based on petrophysical lab measurements [43]. Saturated conditions without groundwater flow were applied.

The BHE is implemented as a particular type of boundary condition, at which it is possible to add or extract a defined amount of heat into the model [50] (Table 1). A dual continuum approach was applied for BHE simulations. It features solving fluid and heat transport processes in the natural subsurface with a 3D finite element approach. The BHE, in contrast, is computed using an analytical solution [48,51,52] coupled to the finite element mesh along with 1D finite element representations. The approach was chosen due to its robustness and reasonable accuracy

Table 1
Parameters of the coaxial BHE.

BHE Geometry	Coaxial
Borehole Diameter	0.2413 m
Inlet Pipe Diameter	0.1143 m
Outlet Pipe Diameter	0.1778 m
Refrigerant thermal conductivity	$0.65 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Refrigerant volumetric heat capacity	$4.145 \text{ MJ m}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Computational Method	Quasi-stationary (Eskilson & Claesson 1988)

[48,49]. However, it can only simulate the global effective thermal conductivity and global resistivity results, as FEFLOW does not accept depth-variable borehole resistances.

3. Results and discussion

This section will initially present a discussion of the GRT results concerning the thermal properties of the subsurface. This will be followed by the presentation of the numerical models for validation purposes. Finally, the internal losses of the borehole heat exchanger and the influences of the various grout sections will be discussed.

3.1. Results of geothermal response test and distributed geothermal response test

Fig. 7 shows the evolution of fluid temperatures, the flow rate, and the calculated heat rate for the GRT. The start of the test is marked by an initial temperature spike, with inlet temperatures reaching up to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ due to pre-heating the buffer tank (Fig. 7a). During the first two days of

Fig. 6. Layout of the numeric model used to validate the results.

Fig. 7. A) flow rate and temperature evolution during the dGRT, b) thermal power injected into the BHE calculated from temperature difference and flow rate according to equation(3).

the GRT, fluctuations in both flow rate and temperature were observed, attributed to the clogging of surface heat exchanger filters by residual particles in the BHE from construction. After cleaning the filters, a stable flow rate of 120 l min^{-1} was achieved, with minor adjustments made throughout the test. Inlet temperatures increased steadily from $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at the start to $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with outlet temperatures following a similar trend, rising from $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The overall heating rate, calculated from the temperature difference between the inlet and outlet and the flow rates, peaked briefly at 700 kW during the initial phase of the test (Fig. 7b) before stabilizing between 125 and 120 kW . Occasional negative outliers corresponded to ambient temperature fluctuations between day and night. The decreasing trend of the heat rate over time reflects the reduced efficiency of the heating unit's internal heat exchanger as the system temperatures increase.

DTS measurements along borehole depth revealed a gradual increase in system temperature over time, with temperatures decreasing from the inner pipe to the outer pipe and grout (Fig. 8). Temperature transitions were especially noticeable at 225 and 465 m , marking the sections with intermediate insulation clearance in the inner pipe and annulus (Fig. 2).

The GRT analysis based on the mean in- and outlet temperature yields a global effective thermal conductivity λ_{eff} of $2.28 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and a global borehole thermal resistance R_b of 0.05 m K W^{-1} . The evaluation based on the average temperature over depth results in an λ_{eff} of $2.25 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ with the regeneration phase and $2.20 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ without considering the regeneration phase. The R_{tb} is, as expected, almost identical, with values of 0.37 m K W^{-1} and 0.35 m K W^{-1} , respectively, when the regeneration phase is included or excluded (Table 2). These results are consistent with values for other coaxial BHE systems [21,53].

The measured thermal conductivity is lower than expected for the granitic rock encountered on site, as laboratory measurements from nearby granite outcrops showed values between 3.1 and $3.3 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. This discrepancy is likely due to the overlying 180 m of altered Basalt with lower thermal conductivities of $1.8 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ measured in the lab. Moreover, the strong alteration of the granite down to a depth of 550 m causes a significant reduction of the thermal conductivity.

The depth-dependent heat output is an important parameter for analyzing the dGRT. The results show that the higher heat output is present in the upper borehole area at the beginning (Fig. 9). This

changes as the test progresses, where the heating power distribution is more homogeneous with slightly higher values in the lower borehole section.

The change in the heat output distribution over the depth is linked to the heating of the BHE. At the beginning, a high-temperature difference between the inner pipe and the annulus yields high heat losses in the upper section of the borehole. Hence the surrounding rock has warmed up and the temperature loss to the annulus has been reduced, more heat is then fed in at the end of the borehole. This change in heat output distribution depends on the properties of the BHE, the grout, and the surrounding rock. This variability was taken in consideration in the dGRT evaluation.

The dGRT provides further insights into the thermal conductivity's depth dependency, with values ranging from 2.0 to $2.6 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and an average of $2.3 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Moreover, the local borehole resistance averages at 0.02 m K W^{-1} . An R^2 value of 0.99 for the model fit indicates a high level of agreement between the line source results and the measured data.

The thermal conductivity varies significantly along the depth, ranging from approximately 2.0 to $2.4 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (Fig. 10a). Near the surface ($0 - 200 \text{ m}$), the conductivity exhibits moderate variation, likely influenced by heterogeneous conditions encountered in the basalt. Starting at 200 m , the thermal conductivity increases from 2.0 to $2.4 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ up to 500 m . Starting from 500 m the values vary in a narrow range of $2.5 - 2.7 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. These findings align with the geological conditions, where granite and granodiorite show a decreasing alteration grade with increasing thermal conductivity with depth. The increase of thermal conductivity in the uppermost borehole section is likely attributed to groundwater flow in the intensively fractured basalt layers, which results in higher effective thermal conductivity. This is also evident from the faster cooling of the uppermost 180 m of the borehole in the recovery phase (Fig. 8).

The thermal borehole resistance decreases steadily with depth. Near-surface values align around 0.04 m K W^{-1} . Much lower values of approximately 0.01 m K W^{-1} were measured at 700 m depth. This trend indicates improved thermal coupling between the BHE and the surrounding rock at greater depths, where more homogeneous lithotypes dominate.

Fig. 8. a) – c) Temperature evolution over depth and time in the inner pipe, the annulus, and the grout of the BHE. d) – e) Temperature over time for multiple depths. The DTS measurements displayed were filtered with a 5 m moving average to reduce temperature fluctuations.

Table 2
Results of the global GRT evaluation.

	λ_{eff} [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	R_b, R_{tb}, R_{tb}^* [m K W ⁻¹]
Mean Temperature Inlet-Outlet, heating phase (R_b)	2.28	0.05
Mean Temperature DTS, heating phase (R_{tb})	2.25	0.03
Mean Temperature DTS, heating and recovery phase (R_{tb}^*)	2.20	0.04

The change from the low to the high conductive grout is marked at a depth of 160 m. It is in the same depth where the lithological transition occurs from Basalt to Granodiorite. Therefore, it is not possible to assess unambiguously which influence is on account of the change in grout composition or from the lithological variation. Hence, the mixed signal of the two effects is examined here. However, the impact of increased borehole resistance should only influence the heating phase, while the lithological effects caused by the fractured basalt occur in the recovery phase, prominently.

Looking at the heating phase it becomes clear that the local borehole resistance is increased in the upper section of the borehole from the ground surface to 190 m (Fig. 10). This is likely due to the influence of the insulating grout, which is performing as intended to, reduce the heat loss into the upper aquifer.

3.2. Numerical validation of the results

The global GRT results were validated through a numerical model using FEFLOW software. The deviation between the measured outlet temperatures of the borehole heat exchanger and the calculated values from FEFLOW is 0.5 °C for the mean inlet and outlet temperature evaluation with R_b . R_{tb}^* yields 0.25 °C when using the average of the DTS temperatures with consideration of the regeneration phase. When only using the heating based on the DTS data the deviation is almost 0 °C (R_{tb}) (Fig. 11). Within the first hours of the test, the deviation is at a maximum of 1.5 °C for all three cases. The simulation did not analyze the cooling phase, as there was no fluid circulation during this phase and therefore no reference inlet and outlet temperatures could be recorded.

Fig. 9. Heating power over depth and time for the dGRT.

Overall, the simulation based on the GRT data provides an accurate match for the experimental results with all three evaluation options, supporting the reliability of the measured values. The method based on the true average temperature offers a superior accuracy compared to the calculation based on purely the inlet and outlet temperature measured on the surface. In contrast, the arithmetic mean simplifies the system by neglecting spatial temperature gradients and local thermal variations, leading to potential inaccuracies in capturing the true heat transfer dynamics [9,21,54].

3.3. Performance of the borehole heat exchanger

When analyzing the BHE performance, it is important to consider that this GRT was conducted at high temperatures reaching up to 70 °C. This temperature level leads to a greater temperature difference between the inner and outer pipe compared to the aforementioned GRT set-ups, where temperature differences are typically around 3.0 – 3.5 °C [20,21]. The increased gradient produces significantly higher heat losses, as larger temperature gradients trigger a higher heat transfer rate.

The heat loss ratio between the inner and outer pipe is almost equal. In total, 49.95 % of the heat input into the BHE is already lost to the outer pipe on its way down the BHE (Fig. 12a). This resulted in a fairly equal heat input rate over the whole borehole length. The largest heat loads are in the upper borehole section at the beginning of the test and a little bigger heat loads in the lower part of the borehole later in the GRT (Fig. 9). The spatial distribution of heat loss from the inner pipe is of particular interest, as it is concentrated at the intermediate open sections (clearances) in the PPR insulation liner. Specifically, 24 % of the total heat loss occurs at the upper clearance and 17 % at the lower clearance

(Fig. 12b). This means that, at 41 %, the insulation clearance accounts for almost half of the total heat loss from the inner to the outer pipe. The distribution of these heat losses shows that the insulation generally effectively reduces overall heat loss as long as the weak points can be addressed.

As pointed out by Holmberg et al. [20], thermal efficiency can be improved generally either by increasing the thermal resistance of the center pipe or by increasing the mass flow rate. Following this, the clearances in the insulation required to allow thermal expansion at a given heat load should be optimized for the expected operating temperatures. A vast temperature range was selected for the given BHE configuration to allow various tests at fluid temperatures of up to 90 °C. In commercial applications, the range of temperature levels to be covered by the MD-BTES should be more closely specified so that the gaps are as small as possible during most operating states. An alternative for the insulation technology used for MD-BTES would be the use of vacuum duplex pipes, whose insulation performance is continuously available over the entire length of the borehole [28]. As used in this setup, coaxial heat exchangers experience low pressure loss [32,55] (approximately 50 kPa in this case for 21 s⁻¹ flow rate), which means that increasing the flow rate can reduce heat loss without increasing pumping power, significantly. This characteristic provides flexibility in managing thermal efficiency in another way, allowing for optimized performance adjustments by controlling flow rates.

The high-temperature delta between the inflow and outflow contributes significantly to the thermal losses observed. For MD-BTES applications, a smaller temperature differential is generally preferred to limit losses, aligning with common industry practices in the use of medium-deep and deep BHE [5,56]. The analysis conducted here refers

Fig. 10. Results of the distributed geothermal response test with effective thermal conductivity (a), borehole thermal resistance (b), and R^2 value (c).

to an exemplary and comparatively extreme operating condition, only.

3.4. Data accuracy and measurement Errors

Both GRT and dGRT results lead to a satisfactory accuracy of numerical simulations based on these results. This means that the system components of the storage system can be reliably dimensioned, which fulfills the main function of the GRT. Nevertheless, a closer look should be taken at individual sources of error and possibilities for improvement in future applications.

In general, glass fiber measurements are very accurate. The temperature resolution specified by the manufacturer is $0.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a spatial resolution of 1 m. In this study, higher deviations from the reference measurements in the water bath of a maximum of $1.5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ were found. However, the mean deviations are considerably lower (Fig. 13). Temperature stratification in the calibration water tank and resulting inaccuracies due to the position of the temperature sensors are potential sources of this mismatch. It is important to note that local variations in attenuation properties due to bending or localized damage to the cable may occur, so comparison with the values measured in the water tank does not necessarily give an indication of the measurement accuracy of the fiber over its entire length [57]. However, calibration over several depth ranges as conducted with the wireline temperature logging in the beginning should minimize these variations.

Additionally, maintaining a stable temperature for the fiber optic controller throughout the experiment is critical, as shifts in the controller's temperature can introduce inaccuracies in the recorded data. Such shifts are challenging to correct, often manifesting as short-term temperature fluctuations in the time series data [12,17]. One option for the correction of temperature drift was presented recently and features a function based on DTS temperature data from the recovery period [57].

The exact positioning of measurement cables relative to the BHE pipes is another factor influencing accuracy. Variations in the position of the fiber optic cables can lead to temperature discrepancies, especially during the heating phase when temperature gradients are most pronounced. This uncertainty highlights the importance of analyzing data from the cooling phase, where a more uniform temperature field is expected, thereby minimizing positional influences on the readings.

The depth-resolved heating power calculation for the dGRT posed a significant challenge, primarily due to the complex and strong interactions between the inner and annular pipes caused by the high-temperature gradient and specific BHE geometry. The inner pipe's influence on the annular temperature field complicated the quantification of heating power for specific sections. Future investigations on similar medium-deep BHE systems may benefit from using an enhanced GRT (eGRT) setup with a heating cable to provide a consistent, depth-constant heating input as demonstrated in multiple studies [58–60].

Fig. 11. BHE outlet temperatures from FEFLOW models compared to the measured outlet temperatures. Outlet temperature (a) and deviation between measured and calculated temperature (b). Zoomed section of the final 5 days of the GRT (c).

Fig. 12. a) comparison of the loss of heat in the inner pipe and the annulus as well as the total heat loss for each time step. b) depth-resolved mean heat losses of the inner pipe over the time of the GRT.

Fig. 13. Comparison of fiberoptic and PT1000 temperature measurements in the calibration water tank.

Alternatively, for simpler determination of depth-dependent heating power in dGRT setups, defining the annulus as the inlet rather than the inner pipe could mitigate the inner pipe's impact on the annular temperature [22]. In this study, the inner pipe was selected as the inlet to simulate realistic storage operation conditions as closely as possible.

4. Conclusions

A dGRT was conducted on one of three 750 m boreholes in an MD-BTES, utilizing fiber optic cables in the annulus, inner pipe, and grout. In addition to the thermal parameters of the BHE and the surrounding rock, the thermal short circuit in the BHE was also investigated. The assessment yielded the following key findings:

1. The GRT was conducted using the in- and outlet temperatures but also by using the true average temperatures from the DTS measurements. Numerical simulations based on the GRT yield a good fit for all datasets, with the highest accuracy achieved using true average temperatures.
2. The distributed GRT (dGRT) analysis reveals significant variation in thermal conductivity along the depth, ranging from 2.0 to 2.8 $\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$, with an average value of 2.3 $\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$. These findings align with the geological conditions, where fractured basaltic units in the uppermost section enhance thermal conductivity due to groundwater flow, while deeper granite and granodiorite exhibit higher conductivity. The relative level of alteration in the plutonics was identified with the dGRT outcomes: increased alteration reduces conductivity. The borehole thermal resistance decreases with depth, from 0.04 m K W^{-1} near the surface to approximately 0.01 m K W^{-1} at 700 m, reflecting improved thermal coupling at greater depths.
3. Improved efficiency can be achieved by increasing the flow rate, reducing the temperature difference, or introducing the fluid flow through the outer pipe instead of the inner pipe, which could minimize cross-pipe thermal short circuits.
4. Up to 60 % of the heat introduced into the top of the borehole reaches the bottom of the borehole despite the insulating PPR liner. The remaining heat is continuously dissipated to the annulus. This

reduces the desired efficiency of the BHE. For later operations, increasing the flow rate and optimizing the design of the clearances in the thermal insulation for the desired temperature range is an option to reduce heat loss.

5. Limited conclusions could be drawn about the performance of the thermal insulating grout which is installed from ground surface to 180 m depth, because lithological conditions are changing strongly from 160 m on. So, the physical influence of grout and geology are interfering. However, it was evident that the borehole thermal resistance was higher in this depth interval compared to the section grouted with high thermal conductivity grout.

These findings demonstrate that GRT methods provide high-quality data even for medium-deep boreholes, offering substantial value for modeling and optimizing the MD-BTES demonstrator in Darmstadt. Additionally, the challenges identified during this study—such as depth-specific heat rate calculation and heat loss management—offer valuable data for improving future designs of medium-deep systems and for operational optimization measures.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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